

WRENCH

Whispers of Time
Heritage as Narratives of Climate Change

D1.1 | Report of the Kick-off meeting of Wrench project

**Universitat Autònoma de
Barcelona, Institute of
History of Science,
18-19 October 2024**

Contents

Participants p.02
Agenda p.03
Activities and debate p.04
Press release and review p.13

A Belmont Forum Project

MAIN AUTHORS

**Samuele Andreoni
Giusy Pappalardo
Marco Armiero**

REVIEWER

Bartolomeo Pantò

Participants

Durham University

Ashraf Osman; Bartolomeo Pantò;
Michael Crang (online)

Durham Castle

Gillian Rennie

Middle East Technical University (METU)

Orta Doğu Teknik Üniversitesi (ODTÜ)
Tugrul Yilmaz

ODTÜ GISAM

Mehmet Olcay Aydemir

Università della Campania “Luigi Vanvitelli”

Corrado Chisari
Michelangelo Scorpio

Diocesi di Ragusa

Giuseppe Occhipinti

Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona (UAB)

Marco Armiero
Giusy Pappalardo
Samuele Andreoni

Coop4Art

Raniero Madonna

Metropolitan City of Naples

Rosario Andreozzi

WRENCH Advisory Board

Manuelina Maria Duarte Cândido (online)
Maria Alessia Glielmi (online)

WELCOME TO
WRENCH

Agenda

First day | October, 18

14:30 - 14:40

Meeting point at UAB's Civic Plaza

15:00 - 15:30

Icebreaker

15:30 - 16:00

Presentation of the project

16:00 - 16:30

Coffee Break

16:30 - 17:10

Presentation of the tasks of each team
(10 minutes per team)

17:10 - 17:30

Non-academic partners' expectations
for WRENCH

17:30 - 18:30

Discussion

Dinner

Second day | October, 19

09:30 - 10:00

Anti-harassment and discrimination
policy for WRENCH, and Data
Management Plan (draft)

10:00 - 11:00

Presentation of the Survey (draft)

11:00 - 11:30

Coffee break

11:30 - 11:45

Coffee Break

11:45 - 12:30

Group discussion:
how to integrate stakeholders and
communities

12:30 - 13:00

Reports from the groups and conclusions

Light lunch

Activities and debate

First day

The meeting started with an interactive game to get to know each other.

Each participant discussed with the person next to them for 5 minutes, and then we asked everyone to introduce their conversation partner to the group.

Presentation of the WRENCH project

Marco Armiero, P.I. of WRENCH, presented the project, highlighting its challenges and key points.

The main points discussed were as follows.

- Main characteristics of WRENCH:
 - the importance of storytelling as a tool for revitalising and mobilising heritage;
 - the central idea of heritage as a living thing, something in which the public and local communities can participate, not just a commodity to be exploited by tourism or other dynamics.

- Methodology:
 - (from the “humanities” side) surveys, focus groups, photo-voice interviews, participant observation and public events. The methodology should be integrated to enhance the participation of citizens and communities in the research process and to co-produce knowledge with them.
 - (from the “engineering” side) non-linear analysis using advanced macro- and mesoscale material descriptions and plastic damage constitutive laws, non-destructive in-situ testing techniques and structural health monitoring methods.
 - VR and other technologies to disseminate project results
- Proposal for webinars:
 - One for each team
 - one on museology (to be defined)
 - one on climatology (to be defined)
- Summer schools (to be defined if online or in situ, a proposal to make 1 in Naples and 1 in Galicia)
- Final conference and the forum of the Mediterranean Cultures at the end of the project (organised by the Città Metropolitana di Napoli)
- Dissemination Plan (suggestions)
- Monthly online meetings

The **Middle East University team**

(**METU-ODTÜ**) presented:

- Climate models and methodology (analysis of climate projection data sets over cultural heritage sites)

The **ODTU GISAM** (Audio-Visual Systems Research and Application Center) presented:

- VR technologies to create a 3D experience around 1 pilot site as a dissemination product of Wrench (impact on the public, choice of pilot site, feasibility).

The **Durham and Vanvitelli team** presented their work in the pilot sites, such as:

- in-situ physical testing of historic materials and structures
- laboratory testing of historic materials under extreme environmental conditions development of rheological models to account for them
- advanced structural modelling
- Numerical models
- 3D models

These methods will provide local communities and visitors with practical evidence of the current and future impacts of extreme climate events on heritage and engage wider audiences.

We have started to discuss

How can these methods be successfully combined in a coherent transdisciplinary project?

Presentation of the tasks of each team

The **UAB team** presented the status of the ongoing coordination tasks and presented a draft plan for the activities to be carried out in the coming months.

main points were discussed:

- Progress in selecting key scholars for a video dictionary
- Selecting stakeholders for a survey/interview

Non-academic partners' expectations for WRENCH

The non-academic partners made some key points about their involvement and expectations.

Giuseppe Occhipinti, representing the **Diocese of Ragusa**, explained the physical risks of the dome about climate change and the means they intend to use in collaboration with the Vanvitelli team. In particular, they presented the idea of installing 3 types of sensors on the tower and the dome to monitor their movements. He then stressed the social and cultural importance of the dome as a heritage site for the local population.

He argued that this project could be really useful and interesting for the city of Ragusa, because the attachment of the population and the central cultural role of the dome are elements that can be used to make the risks of climate change more visible on a larger scale than the dome itself.

Gillian Rennie, representing **Durham Castle**, expressed her commitment to the academic team and explained to the group the social role the castle plays in the community today. The castle is home to a permanent group of university students who actively live in the space. This community could be the main target of the dissemination programme and it represents a perfect opportunity for the project to analyse real practices of living heritage to be exported and proposed to other pilot sites.

In conclusion, Rosario Andreozzi (**Metropolitan City of Naples**) and Raniero Madonna (**Coop4Art**) expressed their pleasure at being involved in the project and presented some proposals, such as the final conference and forum in Naples and the ex-military hospital (pilot site to be confirmed) as a possible location for the summer school. Naples is a city in which material and immaterial heritage are deeply intertwined, and both find the city a perfect place to explore the project.

During this activity, an interactive exercise was proposed to the group.

The idea was to write some expectations for Wrench (from both academic and non-academic partners) on a post-it and stick it on a whiteboard. Here is a summary of the main points that were highlighted

Team's Expectations

- Engage different abilities thanks to the multidisciplinary approach of the project (crossing disciplinary and academic boundaries)
- Have a better gender balance
- Ability to use most storytelling and video content to disseminate project outcomes
- Be able to produce results and negotiate project outcomes with communities and stakeholders
- Write a collective article
- Effectively changing policies and practices
- Integration of multiple external skills into the project
- Restitution to communities in heritage sites → Helping to improve the well-being of the sites and not just publishing (mapping degraded areas, installing monitoring systems, doing things useful for the people).
- Guarantee public access to the project (work in progress and results)

Discussion

The main points raised are the following

- Coordinate publications and conferences as a team (to be defined)
 - make a schedule of possible conferences to assess if there is room for a common plan (Dhuram)
- Coordinate the preparation of the community plans
- Choose the site for the VR simulation (likely to be Durham Castle, to be confirmed)
- Involve new Masters or PhD students in the project
- Expand our constellation of contacts

Second day

We began by discussing harassment and discrimination through an interactive activity, asking ourselves "what is harassment, what is discrimination" based on our experiences and perspectives. Each participant had 10 minutes to write a note, which was collected on a common poster (and reported on page 12 of this document).

Anti-harassment and discrimination policy for WRENCH

Giusy presented the D1.2 deliverable "Anti-harassment and discrimination policy for WRENCH", which contains ethical principles, visions and guidelines to prevent harassment and discrimination. We all had hard copies of this short flyer and took the time to read it carefully. The leaflet also contains a clear indication of what to do if someone is a victim or becomes aware of discrimination and harassment within WRENCH.

Giusy emphasised that this doesn't only apply to the working environment of each research team, nor only to the people present in the room (including non-academic partners): The leaflet has also been prepared in view of the fact that we will be doing fieldwork with more community partners and that we will be working in collective environments. For this reason, it is important to agree on some common principles and norms of behaviour, based on the idea that we want to maintain a horizontal, non-hierarchical asset. Finally, we have focused on the fact that each institution has its norms and procedures, depending on the context in which it is located, and that each partner needs to take them into account carefully.

Given that one of the European references for 'Ethics in research and data management' is the (EU) 2016/679 General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), and that this relates to the D.1.3 deliverable 'Data management plan', we also took time to discuss a first draft prepared by the University of Durham and presented by Bartolomeo Pantò.

Data Management Plan (draft)

Bartolomeo presented the first version of the Data Management Plan (draft), highlighting some points that needed to be clarified, which led to a debate.

A. Are we considering research activities that will involve sensitive data, i.e. data relating to the following categories? i) Racial or ethnic origin; ii) political opinions; iii) religious or philosophical beliefs; iv) trade union membership; v) genetic data; vi) biometric data used for identification; vii) health data; viii) sex life or sexual orientation. If so, how will we store the data securely and anonymously, and how will we ensure anonymity in the publication of research results?

B. Do we need to set up a common online archive with a large data storage capacity?

C. How will we ensure that the data produced by WRENCH is openly accessible?

D. Are the signed letters of support from non-academic partners attached to the proposal submitted to the Belmont Forum sufficient to clarify the ownership and use of the data produced by WRENCH?

We need to ask for similar letters from the new non-academic partners.

E. What should we do if, in the course of our research, we discover something that we think may be dangerous to the public?

On point A, we've agreed that we will include a statement in the plan, but we will be flexible to adapt it on a case-by-case basis, depending on the specific situation..

Regarding point B, Durham University will check with their IT service to see if they can provide a large and shared online archive. We currently use an ICREA archive and a Google profile for email communication and to store shared documents.

We'll discuss point C in more detail at one of the next online meetings.

Regarding point D, we should clarify whether letters of support are sufficient for the time being, considering the possibility of integrating them with clear procedures for data management between academic and non-academic partners.

With regard to point E, we have agreed that, in the event of a critical case, there will be an urgent internal discussion with the support of the Advisory Board to see how to deal with it.

Presentation of the Survey (draft)

We discussed and tested the survey together and identified some errors and pitfalls that needed to be corrected. First, Gillian, a native English speaker, volunteered to do some editing to make some phrases more appropriate and to rephrase some questions (e.g. How do you think research can support your work to address the impact of climate change on heritage? - or: how can research help to address the impact of climate change on cultural heritage?)

We also need to correct some errors in the questions on age and education (some categories are missing). Some questions should be optional and can be skipped (e.g. the question "Do you think that climate change is affecting heritage?")

We should check that the branching works when the survey is accessed by mobile phone. A question can be added asking if the respondent lives/works near a heritage site.

Group discussion: how to integrate stakeholders and communities at large in the activity of the WRENCH project?

Firstly, we have made it clear that we want to work with **three groups of non-academic partners** (the so-called "stakeholders", although we have expressed some critical positions on the use of this word).

- The partners supporting the WRENCH project in each pilot site (first circle of engagement);
- Those groups, organisations, etc. that can be reached by the first group (second circle of engagement);
- People living in the heritage sites; the general public (third circle of engagement).

Over the past few months, some ideas have already emerged as to how we can involve non-academic partners at each level. In particular, we have already shared some preliminary ideas, such as

- Theatre events (with the support of the partner DOM);
- A forum on climate change and heritage in the Mediterranean (with the support of the Metropolitan City of Naples, which has also committed itself to supporting the event from an economic and organisational point of view);
- Community plans in each pilot site of the project, starting with Naples, where Coop4Arts can provide support in organising the process;
- Assistance in carrying out the survey, in-situ testing and measurements. Interaction with UK associations that manage historic assets (Durham Castle);
- Assistance in accessing historical documentation on the Duomo of S. Giorgio; videos, interviews, etc. during the celebrations for S. Giorgio to document the relationship between the heritage building and the local community (with the support of the Diocese of Ragusa).

In order to discuss these ideas in depth and add more, we split up and conducted 3 focused groups of one hour.

Reports from the groups

Group 1

This group has started to exchange concrete ideas on two pilot sites: Ragusa and Naples. Regarding Ragusa, Giuseppe has pointed out that several different individuals and associations with an interest in heritage can be involved, including residents' organisations, owners of historic buildings, local entrepreneurs, etc. In addition, two specific events have been identified as strategic to reach the wider public:

- A literary festival called "A tutto volume", where we can propose to have a space to present and discuss one of the books related to WRENCH, in the presence of the author (we thought of Marco's Wastocene as part of the theoretical framework we are working with);
- The involvement of the Civic Museum of Ragusa, which has Augmented Reality visors and other technological devices ready to host videos and other virtual materials generated by WRENCH, through temporary exhibitions.

With regard to Naples, Roberto has recalled the history of social movements and protests for environmental justice and his work with 32 grassroots organisations that can be contacted to participate in WRENCH. Specifically, having committed to organise and support the "Forum on Climate Change and Heritage in the Mediterranean" in 2026, Roberto considers it important to have a preparatory process that can start a year earlier (2025), with the involvement of social movements and citizens, linking the discussion on heritage with the right to housing and, more generally, with the right to the city.

The preparatory event of the Forum (2025) can be both a scientific and a popular event (including a theatre performance organised with Lello Serrao), where different types of knowledge (academic and local) can intersect. The idea is to produce a White Paper to be presented and discussed at the 2026 Forum, with the mayors or institutional delegates of the main Mediterranean cities, in order to sign an official document of commitments on heritage and climate change.

Group 2

This group initially focused on the issue of identifying specific targets and distinguishing between institutions/policy makers and other stakeholders (e.g. conservationists, NGOs, other community organisations, individuals, etc.). Two main points were discussed in order to clarify the role of potential stakeholders.

- What characteristics should a stakeholder have to participate in this project?
- Our approach is based on planting a non-touristic and consumerist use of heritage to promote a living form of heritage: how can we promote this approach?

Before involving stakeholders and communities, we also need to ask ourselves: how can the outcomes of the project be relevant to them? How can they benefit from the project? How can WRENCH's findings be translated into policy recommendations? Who do we need to talk to in order to do this (in Italy, for example, Soprintendenze, Ministeri, etc.)?

All this information should be clear to the stakeholders we are talking to.

At the community level, the group agreed that public events, information materials and theatre events could be key activities to involve the wider community. At the level of NGOs or governmental organisations, it is important to strengthen WRENCH's online presence to make the project visible and to improve connections, links and international relations with other organisations.

Group 3

This group has highlighted the strategic role of the D5.7 Deliverable, Community Plans, as a means of engaging different stakeholders as well as community members at large in each pilot site. Stakeholders include our universities. We, as part of universities, are also stakeholders and the involvement of our colleagues and students can be key to WRENCH. Within universities we can find other allies who can help to further the debate on the relationship between heritage and climate change. Universities can also play a key role in organising summer schools (the 2.3 deliverable), which can be another strategic tool. The key role of summer schools for WRENCH is twofold.

- On the one hand, they can be opportunities to engage early career researchers interested in heritage and climate change and enrich the diversity of contributions to the debate.
- Secondly, when organised in partnership with local stakeholders and communities, they are a way of encouraging the involvement of a wide range of non-academic actors in the project's activities.

Finally, the group confirmed what had been discussed in other groups: the importance of using theatre events as dissemination events for each pilot site (the D5.6 deliverable), and discussed the possibility of finding some complementary economic resources to support the work of DOM in each site.

Conclusions

Marco concluded the kick-off meeting by saying that we had had two intense and rich days and that the contributions of all the participants had made these two days full of impulses to move the project forward. We have made several decisions, but some points need to be discussed in more detail.

- The data management plan based on GDPR.
- The pilot site where we'll make the virtual reality video (it could be Durham Castle, but we'll see if it's possible to integrate it with other short videos in all the pilot sites to have a final video of WRENCH that includes all the stories we're working with).
- We need to identify the representative of the early career researchers involved in WRENCH (this could be done on a rotating basis).
- We need to discuss how we see the WRENCH website as a "Living Heritage Platform".

There will be dedicated online meetings for this and other topics, and the UAB will circulate the agenda in advance so that everyone can come prepared.

We'll set up a Whatsapp group for those who have agreed, so that we can communicate easily.

Notes from the interactive session

Multiples perspectives of harassment and discrimination

We report on the different ways in which each participant defined harassment and discrimination. In the diversity and richness of perspectives, there is a common thread that links all these statements: the importance of mutual respect and the recognition of the value of differences. The following statements have been included in the D.2 deliverable "Anti-harassment and discrimination policy for WRENCH".

"For me, harassment is habits or behaviors that may offend, or violate (physically or mentally) someone. I am used to associating it with sexual violence. Discrimination is a way to stay in our ignorance fighting everything or everybody different in culture, gender, habits"

"Harassment is for me any behavior that is violent in many ways – physically and verbally – and disrespectful. Discrimination is excluding the powerless".

"Harassment is when your behavior puts someone uncomfortable or makes someone scared. Discrimination is when you judge someone based on the group they belong to (ethnic/religion/gender)"

"Harassment is persuading and manipulating, is verbal pestering, not listening to other's views, feelings. Discrimination is preconceived ideas, automatic mining way to tell about myself, my protected characteristics."

"Harassment is the tendency of some workplaces (or higher-rank workers) to create work relationships which inhibit the full exploitation of capacity, enthusiasm, potential of colleagues, especially younger and more diverse ones. Discrimination is the act of making decisions about work division, tasks, distributions, or simpler ones about ordinary life, considering aspects that are not relevant to the case"

"Harassment is trying to make others feel uncomfortable or make them lose confidence. Discrimination is not giving equal opportunities to everyone"

"Harassment is behaviors that annoy the others. Discrimination is behaviors or discourses which will make other people feel excluded, negative, discouraged"

"Harassment and discrimination are the worst postures for a group of people, bullying behaviors"
"Harassment is when you force someone to do something he/she dislikes. Discrimination is when someone is excluded for his/her physical characteristics or different ideas"

"Harassment is a way to treat colleagues in a diminishing way, for example not considering difficulties, opinions, and needs when making decisions. Of course, harassment is any kind of violence, physical or psychological, linked to any type of discrimination (gender, race, physical abilities, and so on)."

"Discrimination is the act of treating someone differently on the base of any reason. Harassment is the act of intruding on one's personal space without the will of that person either physically or mentally"

"Harassment is any form of abuse of power. In a male-dominated society, we often do not even recognize harassment. Harassment should not be defined by those in power but by those who are victims. Discrimination is conscious and unconscious bias based on unjust power relations".

Napoli

Climate change e patrimonio storico-artistico: WRENCH, Napoli protagonista a Barcellona

© SudNotizie.com 21 Ottobre 2024 15:29

I cambiamenti climatici non influiscono solo sulle nostre vite, ma anche sui monumenti e sul patrimonio storico-artistico dei territori, accelerando i processi di degradazione. A rispondere a queste problematiche, è stato lanciato il progetto internazionale "WRENCH - Whispers of Time. Heritage as Narratives of Climate Change", che ha visto la sua inaugurazione il 18 e 19 ottobre presso l'Istituto di Storia della Scienza dell'Università Autonoma di Barcellona (UAB). Alla conferenza ha partecipato **Rosario Andreozzi**, Consigliere metropolitano delegato all'Ambiente della **Città Metropolitana di Napoli**, che ha ufficialmente aderito all'iniziativa.

Il progetto WRENCH è sostenuto dal **Belmont Forum**, un organismo internazionale che promuove la ricerca transdisciplinare sui cambiamenti climatici. Coordinato dalla UAB, coinvolge partner accademici come la **Middle East Technical University**, la **Durham University**, l'**Università della Campania Vanvitelli**, e soggetti non accademici come **Hidromod**, **Coop4Art**, **DOM**, la **Diocesi di Ragusa** e il **Castello di Durham**.

"La nostra adesione - ha affermato **Andreozzi** - riflette l'importanza di tutelare il patrimonio storico, artistico, architettonico e paesaggistico della nostra città, profondamente esposto agli effetti del cambiamento climatico". Ha inoltre annunciato la volontà di proporre una tappa del progetto a Napoli per l'anno successivo e di partecipare alla costruzione di un Forum **Mediterraneo** su cambiamenti climatici e patrimonio, seguendo le indicazioni del Sindaco **Gaetano Manfredi**.

I ricercatori del progetto WRENCH svilupperanno metodi per valutare la vulnerabilità del **patrimonio culturale** ai cambiamenti climatici, proponendo strategie di adattamento. Verrà esplorato l'impatto delle condizioni climatiche estreme, come temperature estreme, vento e precipitazioni, sui materiali storici come **tufo**, mattoni e calcestruzzo, oltre al rischio di catastrofi naturali.

Saranno scelti cinque siti pilota tra il Regno Unito e i Paesi del Mediterraneo, e **Napoli** sarà uno di questi. "Stiamo valutando il **Cimitero delle Fontanelle** e altri luoghi del nostro patrimonio per lo studio dell'impatto del cambiamento climatico e per sperimentare nuove pratiche di conservazione", ha annunciato **Andreozzi**.

<https://www.sudnotizie.com/climate-change-e-patrimonio-storico-artistico-wrench-napoli-protagonista-a-barcellona/>

Last access: November 26, 2024

Press release and review

Napoli

📍 Cambiamenti Climatici, Città Metropolitana Di Napoli, Conservazione, Degrado Monumenti, Forum Mediterraneo, Patrimonio Culturale, Rosario Andreozzi, Tutela Patrimonio, Università Autonoma Di Barcellona, WRENCH

👤 Francesco Belliofatto 📅 Ottobre 21, 2024 💬 0 Commenti

Climate change e patrimonio storico-artistico: WRENCH, Napoli protagonista a Barcellona

I cambiamenti climatici non influiscono solo sulle nostre vite, ma anche sui monumenti e sul patrimonio storico-artistico dei territori, accelerando i processi di degradazione. A rispondere a queste problematiche, è stato lanciato il progetto internazionale "WRENCH – Whispers of Time. Heritage as Narratives of Climate Change", che ha visto la sua inaugurazione il 18 e 19 ottobre presso l'Istituto di Storia della Scienza dell'Università Autonoma di Barcellona (UAB). Alla conferenza ha partecipato Rosario Andreozzi, Consigliere metropolitano delegato all'Ambiente della Città Metropolitana di Napoli, che ha ufficialmente aderito all'iniziativa.

Il progetto WRENCH è sostenuto dal **Belmont Forum**, un organismo internazionale che promuove la ricerca transdisciplinare sui cambiamenti climatici. Coordinato dalla UAB, coinvolge partner accademici come la **Middle East Technical University**, la **Durham University**, l'Università della Campania Vanvitelli, e soggetti non accademici come **Hidromod**, **Coop4Art**, **DOM**, la **Diocesi di Ragusa** e il **Castello di Durham**.

"La nostra adesione – ha affermato **Andreozzi** – riflette l'importanza di tutelare il patrimonio storico, artistico, architettonico e paesaggistico della nostra città, profondamente esposto agli effetti del cambiamento climatico". Ha inoltre annunciato la volontà di proporre una tappa del progetto a Napoli per l'anno successivo e di partecipare alla costruzione di un Forum Mediterraneo su cambiamenti climatici e patrimonio, seguendo le indicazioni del Sindaco **Gaetano Manfredi**.

I ricercatori del progetto WRENCH svilupperanno metodi per valutare la vulnerabilità del patrimonio culturale ai cambiamenti climatici, proponendo strategie di adattamento. Verrà esplorato l'impatto delle condizioni climatiche estreme, come temperature estreme, vento e precipitazioni, sui materiali storici come tufo, mattoni e calcestruzzo, oltre al rischio di catastrofi naturali.

Saranno scelti cinque siti pilota tra il Regno Unito e i Paesi del Mediterraneo, e **Napoli** sarà uno di questi. "Stiamo valutando il **Cimitero delle Fontanelle** e altri luoghi del nostro patrimonio per lo studio dell'impatto del cambiamento climatico e per sperimentare nuove pratiche di conservazione", ha annunciato **Andreozzi**.

<https://www.sudenord.it/2024/10/21/climate-change-e-patrimonio-storico-artistico-wrench-napoli-protagonista-a-barcellona/>

Last access: November 26, 2024

Press release and review

Il 18 e 19 ottobre 2024 si è svolto l'evento di lancio del progetto internazionale "WRENCH" (Whispers of Time. Heritage as Narratives of Climate Change), presso l'Università Autonoma di Barcellona (UAB), coordinato dal Prof. Marco Armiero, storico dell'ambiente di fama internazionale. La due giorni ha affrontato il tema di come il cambiamento climatico sta avendo un impatto crescente e duraturo sul nostro ambiente e sulla società, con una particolare attenzione sul patrimonio culturale – materiale e immateriale – minacciato da rischi noti, nuovi e più estremi. I ricercatori hanno già studiato gli impatti dei cambiamenti climatici sull'ambiente, sui sistemi sociali e sull'economia, tuttavia, poiché il patrimonio artistico diventa sempre più vulnerabile, c'è ancora molto da fare per integrare le scoperte esistenti, coinvolgere le società nelle discussioni sulla tematica e migliorare il grado di resilienza, al fine di sviluppare solide politiche e strategie di prevenzione e adattamento.

Il Workshop che rientra tra le iniziative di programmazione congiunta Cultural Heritage and Global Change (JPI CH) e Connecting Climate Knowledge for Europe (JPI Climate) , sostenuta dal Belmont Forum, vede la partecipazione di un ampio partenariato, formato da istituzioni accademiche (Middle East Technical University; Durham University; Università della Campania Vanvitelli) e soggetti non accademici, tra cui la Città Metropolitana di Napoli, Hidromod, Coop4Art, DOM, la Diocesi di Ragusa e il Castello di Durham.

Nella delegazione italiana era presente Rosario Andreozzi, Consigliere Delegato all'Ambiente e alla Biodiversità della Città Metropolitana di Napoli, storico attivista ambientale e sociale, che nella due giorni ci ha spiegato che *"il progetto WRENCH mira a indagare la relazione tra patrimonio territoriale e cambiamenti climatici con un approccio che spazia tra la storia ambientale, l'antropologia, le scienze umane per l'ambiente, l'ingegneria e la pianificazione di comunità" – " questo percorso per una città come Napoli diventa fondamentale per sviluppare una metodologia che coinvolga le scienze ambientali, le discipline umanistiche e la comunità, per studiare e affrontare l'impatto dei cambiamenti climatici sul patrimonio storico e artistico" – "La Città Metropolitana di Napoli, con il Sindaco Manfredi ha aderito formalmente al progetto e contribuirà, nei prossimi mesi, al processo di costruzione di un Forum dei Paesi del Mediterraneo su cambiamenti climatici e l' impatto sul patrimonio culturale, per contribuire al cambiamento delle politiche a livello globale sui temi dell' ecologia".*

<https://www.rossoambientalista.it/2024/10/21/wrench-la-difesa-del-patrimonio-culturale-dai-cambiamenti-climatici/>
Last access: November 26, 2024

Press release and review

REPORT
Vesuviano

HOME NEWS POLITICA CRONACA EVENTI SPORT

Cambiamenti Climatici E Patrimonio: Progetto Internazionale "WRENCH – Whispers Of Time. Heritage As Narratives Of Climate Change" Con L'adesione Di Città Metropolitana Di Napoli

Di Redazione Ottobre 21, 2024

TUTTI GLI ARTICOLI

AAA

Il 18 e 19 ottobre 2024 si è svolto l'evento di lancio del progetto internazionale "WRENCH – Whispers of Time. Heritage as Narratives of Climate Change", presso l'Università Autonoma di Barcellona (UAB), Istituto di Storia della Scienza.

Il progetto WRENCH mira a indagare la relazione tra patrimonio territoriale e cambiamenti climatici con un approccio che spazia tra la storia ambientale, l'antropologia, le scienze umane per l'ambiente, l'ingegneria e la pianificazione di comunità. Il progetto metterà in luce diverse storie emblematiche raccontate dal patrimonio "vivente", fatto non solamente da edifici monumentali e siti archeologici ma anche da fiumi, monti, boschi, laghi e, soprattutto dalle persone che abitano i luoghi, in 5 siti pilota individuati tra il Regno Unito e i Paesi del Mediterraneo.

Il progetto è sostenuto dal Belmont Forum, organismo internazionale che promuove la ricerca trans-disciplinare sui cambiamenti climatici a scala globale.

WRENCH è coordinato dalla UAB e vede la partecipazione di un ampio partenariato, formato da istituzioni accademiche (Middle East Technical University; Durham University; Università della Campania Vanvitelli) e soggetti non accademici, tra cui Hidromod, Coop4Art, DOM, la Diocesi di Ragusa e il Castello di Durham.

La Città Metropolitana di Napoli ha aderito formalmente al progetto e contribuirà, nei prossimi mesi, al processo di costruzione di un Forum dei Paesi del Mediterraneo su cambiamenti climatici e patrimonio. Rosario Andreozzi, Consigliere metropolitano delegato all'ambiente, ha partecipato all'evento portando il sostegno convinto dell'istituzione.

<https://www.reportvesuviano.it/2024/10/21/cambiamenti-climatici-e-patrimonio-progetto-internazionale-wrench-whispers-of-time-heritage-as-narratives-of-climate-change-con-ladesione-di-citta-metropolitana-di-napo/>
Last access: November 26, 2024

WRENCH

*Whispers of Time
Heritage as Narratives
of Climate Change*

A Belmont Forum Project
2024

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18625497>

PCI2024-153536

